

GENERAL ISSUES IN PREPARING AND ANNOTATING CORPORA

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1 INTRODUCTION

A corpus is rarely a collection of raw texts grouped together. To derive meaning from corpora, we normally need to first (i) remove noise or unwanted text; (ii) divide the corpus into segments (normally tokens and sentences); (iii) add layers of annotation (or information) to the text; and (iv) document and store information about the text itself. These pieces of information should be ideally structured in a way that allows them to be easily retrieved in a corpus.

2 PREPROCESSING

Annotation is better done to a raw text, without extra information other than the text itself. However, some pre-processing to normalise the text is desirable (Wolfe, 2002; Dash, 2021). For matters of clarity, in this text, we divide this pre-processing into two groups: cleaning and data preparation.

2.1 CLEANING

Cleaning refers to removing noise or unwanted information from the text. These undesirable elements can be, for example, page headings and footnotes, page numbers, sensitive data, and boilerplates (text fragments repeated without major changes). In some cases, the cleaning has to be done manually (e.g. search for sensitive data). Very often, the cleaning can be done (semi) automatically with the identification of mark-up tags and the use of regular expressions.

Once the cleaning is completed, the discarded data cannot be accessed anymore. This is the first version of the corpus and is normally kept as canonical raw data. It is also at this point that the information about each text (metadata) is documented (see section 4)

2.2 DATA PREPARATION

2.2.1 Segmentation: tokens and sentences

Tokenization and segmentation are steps performed in the earlier stages of most text analyses.

It is normally a fast process done using deterministic algorithms (e.g. Bird et al., 2009) to establish token and sentence boundaries (Grefenstette, 1999).

Some examples of commonly used tokenizers are OpenNLP¹, SpaCy², and TreeTagger (Schmid, 1994). For an evaluation of state-of-the-art tokenization tools for German, see Diewald et al.

(2022). Understanding (and customizing) the segmentation process is opportune when choosing a tokenizer, as they might vary on how they account for multiword expressions and ambiguous separators, for example. Inexact tokenization can negatively affect later processes and applications with the corpus. For instance, running a dependency parser (see 3.1) on a badly tokenized sequence yields errors beyond the span of the problematic token or sentence.

2.2.2 Data filtering

Depending on the type of analysis that will follow, it might be necessary to remove unwanted tokens that affect the statistical analysis. This is normally done by using a stopword list to filter the texts. Stopwords, or empty words, are, usually, words commonly used in a language, such as prepositions and articles. Punctuations might also be filtered out of a corpus, especially when spoken data is concerned. However, they are crucial to identify boundaries and context (e.g. questions, exclamation, citation) (Jurafsky & Martin, 2021:11).

2.2.3 Normalization

Words might have different spellings that should be preserved or normalized, depending on the research question. When variation of orthography is not relevant, a common step is to normalize the text by establishing a standard for words with alternative spellings.

Another way of normalization, which is especially done with highly inflected languages, is the replacement of the tokens for its lemma (base word form) or stem (word root). Although this step is here described as a preprocessing step, a lower level of annotation is necessary (see 3.1).

¹ <https://opennlp.apache.org/>

² <https://spacy.io/>

3 IN-TEXT ANNOTATION

Adding extra information to the texts makes analyses easier and more precise (see General Issues in Data Analysis). Annotation can add different layers of knowledge to text. It can be related to grammar, meaning, orthography, etc. Leech (1993:275) proposes seven maxims of text annotation, from which we emphasize the following three:

- “It should always be easy to dispense with annotation and revert to the raw corpus.” (1)
- “(...) the annotated corpus is made available to a research community on a caveat emptor principle.” (5)
- “(...) to avoid misapplication, annotation schemes should preferably be based as far as possible on ‘consensual’, and ‘theory-neutral analyses’ of the corpus data”. (6)

There are many categorization schemes for the different types of annotation (see, e.g., Dash 2021). For matters of clarity and to avoid theory bias, we follow The IMS Open Corpus Workbench (CWB) encoding manual (Evert, 2022; Evert & Hardie 2011) and divide the annotation types into positional (token-level) and structural (region-level) attributes.

3.1 TOKEN-LEVEL

Token-level annotation is normally done automatically, attributing a value to each token in the corpus. Common types of annotation of this type are part-of-speech annotation (POS), also known as grammatically annotation, and lemma. Token-level annotation might also indicate the relationship among different tokens, as is the case when parsing a text (adding syntactic annotation).

Some common tools for token-level annotation tools are Tree tagger, Spacy, Spark³, and Freeling (Padró & Stanilovsky, 2012). Among the most frequently referred standards, we can cite CLAWS, the Constituent Likelihood Automatic Word-tagging System (Garside, 1987); the EAGLE annotation guideline (Ide & Suderman, 2014); TEI, Text Encoding Initiative (Sperberg-McQueen & Burnard, 1994); and Universal Dependencies (UD)⁴.

3.2 REGION-LEVEL

Leech (1993) makes the distinction between (a) representation and (b) interpretative information that can be annotated to a text. The first refers to the structure and the form of a

³ <https://www.johnsnowlabs.com/>

⁴ <https://universaldependencies.org/>

text. It can be sentence boundaries (see 2.2.1), pauses, words, and spellings. Interpretative, however, refers to the ‘hidden’ information in the text and is normally done manually by experts.

This type of annotation is particularly useful to restrict the corpus queries to specific corpus regions (see General Issues in Data Analysis).

4 METADATA

Properly recording information about the text such as date of publication, author’s name, language variety and source is useful for the data analysis and for the annotation itself. For example, specifying the language variety can help in the decision of the best language model for automatic tagging.

Metadata is normally stored as headers in all texts that compose a corpus (e.g. TEI header). Storing the metadata in tabular format is also common practice (e.g., Hardie, 2012).

5 FORMAT

The previous sections discussed the different ways of obtaining and adding information to a corpus before proceeding to the analysis. However, the way this information is stored varies.

Corpora are often prepared using XML. TEI is a frequently adopted standard. However, there are simplified suggestions, such as Hardie (2014), which do not impose strict rules. Simplified versions of TEI might be a good choice for smaller projects.

To make a corpus ready for query systems such as CWB and Manatee (Rychlý, 2007), we need the corpus formatted in a vertical format (vrt). This means each token is represented in a line and its respective tags are added to subsequent columns (see Evert, 2022).

The decision of how to format the corpus is normally made according to how the analysis will be performed. The section General Issues in Data Analysis deals with that.

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